

Methods for identifying informative features in agricultural images

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ABSTRACT

The paper deals with informative aspects of images, their scope and extraction methods. The research addresses numerous different types of features such as texture, color, geometric and structural features that play an important role in the field of image analysis and recognition. Contemporary extraction methods based on machine learning algorithms and fractal dimension are explained. The possibility of usage of these methods in real-life problems such as medical imaging, biometrics, remote sensing images processing and agriculture is considered. Successful implementation examples of information functions in real-life problems are presented and opportunities for further research on the topic are considered.

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1. INTRODUCTION

It needs effective feature extraction techniques that may be employed to recognize, classify, and segment objects within an image [1]. Features play a crucial role in the reduction and acceleration of data processing as well as the improvement of the accuracy of recognition. The importance of this step in the sequence of the process of images cannot be overemphasized since the success of the subsequent steps of analysis largely depends on the quality of the features selected [2]. This paper shall present a class of techniques that may be used to determine the most informative features of an image. Computer vision and image processing continue gaining popularity among many disciplines in the field of science and technology. This paper will discuss the family of methods allowing the determination of the most informative and important characteristics of an image. Computer vision and the processing of images have become popular on a global level in the areas of science and technology [3]. One of the most important steps of the process of the analysis of an image is the definition of informative characteristics, which are compressed and generalized data characterizing the image [4]. Computer vision and the processing of images continue to become popular

on a global level in the areas of science and technology. One of the most important steps of the process of the analysis of an image is the extraction of informative characteristics, which are compressed and generalized data characterizing the image [5].

The literature review examines modern image processing techniques, including automated nuclear receptor localization analysis [1], elevation map reconstruction using radar images [2], deep learning for surface debris detection [3], and fire segmentation in drone images [4]. The approaches to improving feature matching [5], classification of diseases in computed tomography (CT) images [6], fractal methods in remote sensing [7], [8], watermark embedding [9], integration of convolutional neural network (CNN) and random sample consensus (RANSAC) for object recognition [10], and other relevant areas in the field of computer vision and image analysis [11]–[20] have been studied.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. Algorithm oriented FAST and rotated BRIEF (ORB) [6]

The methodology proposed in this study involves converting input images into vector representations by extracting key informative features using the ORB algorithm [10]. ORB combines two foundational algorithms: features from accelerated segment test (FAST) for identifying key points, and binary robust independent elementary features (BRIEF) for computing descriptors [21]. The process begins with the detection of informative points across the image using the FAST algorithm. For each candidate pixel, the surrounding 16-pixel circular neighborhood is evaluated to determine whether it constitutes a key point [22]. A pixel is classified as informative if the following condition is met for any subset of contiguous pixels on the circle [11]:

let, $I(p) - p$ be the intensity in pixels. If circle C contains n adjacent sets of pixels, then pixel p is considered the base point.

$$I(p) - I(p_i) > \text{doorstep}, \text{ or } I(p_i) - I(p) > \text{doorstep} \quad (1)$$

here, p_i is each pixel inside the circle.

The ORB algorithm is designed to transform images into feature vectors, enabling tasks such as object recognition and image matching. This conversion process is structured into four key stages, each building upon the previous one to generate reliable binary descriptors. The overall workflow of the ORB algorithm is depicted in Figure 1. It starts with an input image and moves through the feature detection phase, which leverages the FAST corner detector to efficiently identify potential keypoints. From this initial set, the Harris corner measure is applied to refine the selection, isolating the most stable and distinctive points. After pinpointing these optimal keypoints, the BRIEF descriptor is computed at each location, resulting in a compact and robust binary representation. The end product is a feature vector representation of the image, ready for use in tasks like matching or recognition.

This step-by-step approach enhances ORB's efficiency in real-time applications, leveraging the computational simplicity of both FAST and BRIEF algorithms. Their integration produces a feature descriptor that is not only resistant to noise but also rotation-invariant, making it ideal for diverse computer vision tasks such as object tracking, image stitching, and visual odometry.

Figure 1. Converting an image to a vector using ORB algorithm

Harris corner measure is used to assess the stability of data points. Harris angular measure is calculated as (2) [12]:

$$R = \det(M) - k(\text{trace}(M))^2 \quad (2)$$

where, M – gradients are the covariance matrix and a k is a constant (usually between 0.04-0.06). The orientation of the ORB informative gradient points is used to determine the formula (3) [23]:

$$\theta = \arctan\left(\frac{\sum_i w_i I(p_i) y_i}{\sum_i w_i I(p_i) x_i}\right) \quad (3)$$

where, w_i is the weight function, and $I(p_i)$ is the pixel intensity.

For descriptor computation, BRIEF performs binary comparisons between pairs of pixels in a smoothed image patch. To ensure rotation invariance, the descriptor coordinates are rotated according to the keypoint orientation [24]:

$$\tau(p, \theta) = (u \cos \theta - v \sin \theta, u \sin \theta + v \cos \theta), \quad (4)$$

where, τ is the rotating coordinates of the descriptor patch, θ is the orientation of the key point, u and v are the coordinates of pairs of pixels [13].

When generating descriptors, the vector is expressed as a bit string:

$$BRIEF(p) = \sum_{i=1}^N 2^{i-1} (I(p) + \tau(u_i, \theta) < I(p) + \tau(v_i, \theta))$$

where, N is the length of the descriptor (for example, 256 bits), I is the pixel intensity, and u_i and v_i are the coordinates of the pixel pairs. ORB descriptors are 32 bits (256 bits) long, each bit is part of a descriptor and represents a texture and other properties around an informative point [25].

2.2. Fractal dimension [7]

Informative features refer to fundamental attributes within an image that carry essential information about its content. These features are critical in tasks such as image recognition, classification, and analysis [14]. In contextual image recognition systems, such features are particularly vital, as their identification enables more effective and accurate image processing [26]. Informative features are widely employed across domains such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, and Earth remote sensing [27].

Some typical informative image features include [15]:

- Edges and borders: The lines, borders, and contours of objects in an image can be important signs of their recognition [16].
- Corners and facet points: Certain points in an image, such as corners, line intersections, or texture nodes, serve as primary markers for highlighting and recognizing objects [17].
- Color properties: Information about the color and color distribution in an image is useful for classifying objects or defining special attributes [18].
- Texture properties: Describing texture properties, such as texture gradients or structural elements, will help in selecting and classifying objects [28].
- Shape and size of objects: Information about the shape, size, and ratio of objects will be important for their identification and classification [19].
- Features of objects: For instance, faces, key points of anatomy, or unique attributes of objects that can be identified in an image [20].

These examples represent a subset of the numerous features that can be extracted for analysis. When various types of features are combined and processed using digital image processing techniques or machine learning models, the accuracy and efficiency of recognition systems can be significantly improved. One such analytical method for structural feature identification is the fractal dimension, which adds an additional layer of spatial complexity to the analysis of image structures [29].

Fractal dimension is a metric used to quantify the complexity or irregularity of a structure, especially in spatially distributed data. In metric spaces, it is used to characterize sets that may not conform to traditional Euclidean dimensions. There are several types of fractal dimensions, including Hausdorff and box-counting dimensions [30]. They are calculated as follows.

Fractal (Hausdorff, box-counting) dimensions are calculated using the formula:

$$d = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow 0} \frac{\ln N(\xi)}{\ln(\frac{1}{\xi})} \tag{6}$$

where, $N(\xi)$ is the minimum number of cubes with a side of ξ , required to cover the entire complex [31]. The measurement is defined as an exponent of the d degree in $N(\xi) \propto \frac{1}{\xi^d}$ as shown in Figure 2.

- Border block allocation: $N(\xi) \propto \frac{L}{\xi}$,
- Division of total volume blocks: $N(\xi) \propto \frac{L}{\xi^2}$,

Another fractal dimension method is the shoreline method: The length of the coastline is measured in l , then the measured length is calculated using the (7) [32].

$$L = \Delta l^\alpha, \Delta = const \tag{7}$$

The box-counting method is implemented through a systematic grid-based measurement technique applied to the target structure. The process is illustrated in Figure 2, which demonstrates the use of the Hausdorff box-counting dimension on a tree structure. In Figure 2(a), the boundary line extraction process is depicted, where the object's contour is transformed into a continuous linear path that represents its geometric complexity for measurement. Figure 2(b) highlights the grid overlay methodology, where boxes of size ϵ are applied over the structure, and shaded boxes indicate interactions with the boundary, contributing to the count $N(\xi)$. This spatial segmentation enables quantification of how the boundary occupies space at specific resolutions. Figure 2(c) illustrates the iterative refinement through seven stages, progressively increasing grid resolution (decreasing ϵ) from left to right. The transition in color from red to grayscale portrays the shift toward finer measurement scales, revealing intricate details of the fractal boundary. By plotting $\log N(\frac{1}{\xi})$ against $\log(\frac{1}{\xi})$ based on these measurements, the fractal dimension is determined from the slope of the resulting linear graph.

Figure 2. Hausdorff box-counting dimension, (a) separation of blocks by boundary line, (b) separation of blocks by total volume, and (c) box-counting

Figure 3 shows traditional ideas about geometry, forms a scale in accordance with predictable, understandable and familiar ideas about the space in which they are located. For example, take a line, divide it into three equal parts, and then each part will be three times less than the length of the original line [33]. It also happens on the plane. If you measure the area of a square and then measure the area of the square by $\frac{1}{\xi}$ the length of the side of the original square, it will be 9 times smaller than the area of the original square. This measurement can be determined mathematically by using the measurement rule according to (8) [34]:

$$N \propto \xi^{-D} \quad (8)$$

where, N is the number of parts, ε is the dimensional coefficient, D is the dimensional coefficient, ∞ is the fractal dimension, which means the proportion in this sign. This scaling rule confirms the traditional rules of geometry scaling, since for a line $N = 3$, when $\xi = \frac{1}{3}$, then $D = 1$, and for squares, because $N = 9$, when $\xi = \frac{1}{3}$, $D = 2$. The same rule applies to fractal geometry, but it is less intuitive. To calculate the unit length of a fractal line, at first glance, reduce the scale three times, in this case $N = 4$, when $\xi = \frac{1}{3}$ and we obtain the value of (8) by changing (9) [35]:

$$\log_{\xi} N = -D \frac{\log N}{\log \xi} \quad (9)$$

Figure 3. The total length of the coastline

2.3. Normalization signs [8]

Following the extraction of key image features, it is necessary to represent these features in a standardized format suitable for subsequent analysis and classification tasks. This section outlines the process by which object areas and their corresponding informative features are quantified and normalized for consistent use in machine learning pipelines [36]. The following metrics are computed for each image and serve as descriptors of its geometric and structural content:

- Contrast: A measure of intensity variation across the image.
- Number of contours (*num_contours*): Total number of distinct object boundaries detected.
- Mean contour area (*mean_contour_area*): The average area enclosed by identified contours.
- Standard deviation of contour area (*std_contour_area*): Variability in the size of detected regions.
- Mean contour perimeter (*mean_contour_perimeter*): Average length of the perimeters of all contours.
- Standard deviation of contour perimeter (*std_contour_perimeter*): Dispersion in the perimeter lengths.
- Mean area-to-perimeter ratio (*mean_area_to_perimeter_ratio*): A shape descriptor capturing object compactness.
- Fractal dimension: A complexity measure that quantifies the self-similarity or irregularity of the object's shape.

Figure 4 displays the progression of box-counting across three dimensions ($D = 1, D = 2$, and $D = 3$) over three iteration levels ($l = 1, l = 2$, and $l = 3$). In the first column ($D = 1$), one-dimensional objects are represented as line segments. At iteration level $l = 1$, there is a single unit line segment with $N = 1$. When subdivided at $l = 2$, the line comprises $N = 2$ segments, and at $l = 3$, N increases to 3 segments, demonstrating a linear relationship where $N = l$. The second column ($D = 2$) depicts square grids in two dimensions. At $l = 1$, the square consists of $N = 1$ unit. This grows to $N = 4$ units at $l = 2$, forming a 2×2 grid, and to $N = 9$ units at $l = 3$, resulting in a 3×3 grid. This scaling follows the relationship $N = l^2$. In the third column ($D = 3$), three-dimensional cubic structures are illustrated. At $l = 1$, there is a single cube ($N = 1$). This count increases to $N = 8$ cubes at $l = 2$, forming a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ configuration, and reaches $N = 27$ cubes at $l = 3$ with a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ configuration. The scaling here follows the formula $N = l^3$. This visualization effectively demonstrates the general scaling law $N = l^D$, which serves as the mathematical basis for calculating fractal dimensions using the box-counting method.

Figure 4. The traditional representation of geometry in measurements and scale determination

The power-law relationship between the number of units and the measurement scale is what sets apart objects of varying dimensionalities and forms the foundation for assessing non-integer fractal dimensions in intricate natural structures. Each of these characteristics corresponds to a feature column in the dataset, representing numerical values that describe an individual image in vector form. These features are critical inputs for classification models, enabling the system to distinguish between image categories based on structural, geometric, and textural patterns.

After identifying informative features, each feature is normalized in the range from 0 to 1 according to formula (10) [37]:

$$I_{i,j}^{normal} = \frac{I_{i,j} - I_{i,j}^{min}}{I_{i,j}^{max} - I_{i,j}^{min}} \tag{10}$$

where, $I_{i,j}^{normal}$ is normalized values, $I_{i,j}$ is input values in the column, $I_{i,j}^{max}$, $I_{i,j}^{min}$ minimum and maximum values of the column. By applying this transformation, all feature vectors are scaled uniformly, ensuring that no single feature disproportionately influences the learning process. This step is essential for maintaining model robustness and optimizing classification performance in high-dimensional image datasets.

2.4. Support vector machine [9]

In this study, the support vector machine (SVM) algorithm was employed for the classification of features extracted from images. This machine learning technique was selected due to its high effectiveness in scenarios involving limited training data and its strong generalization capability across diverse datasets. At the initial stage of the classification pipeline, key informative features were extracted from the input images using a combination of ORB feature detection and fractal dimension analysis. These features encapsulated both geometric and textural properties of the target objects. The resulting feature vectors were subsequently normalized, as outlined in section 2.3, and served as input to the SVM classifier.

SVM is a well-established supervised learning algorithm particularly suited for binary classification tasks. The core idea behind SVM is the identification of an optimal separating hyperplane within the feature space that maximizes the margin between data points belonging to different classes. This margin maximization strategy contributes significantly to the model's generalization performance. The SVM operates through the following sequence of steps, enabling effective classification of images based on the extracted features:

2.4.1. Linear support vector machine

Given a labeled training dataset:

$$\{(x_i, y_i)\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, x_i \in \mathbb{R}^d, y_i \in \{-1, +1\} \tag{10}$$

where x_i is a feature vector extracted from an image and y_i is the corresponding class label, SVM seeks to find the optimal separating hyperplane, n is number of training examples [38].
The goal of SVM is to find a hyperplane:

$$w^T x + b = 0 \quad (11)$$

that maximizes the margin between the two classes. The optimization problem is formulated as:

$$\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \quad (12)$$

subject to the constraint:

$$y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1, \forall i \quad (13)$$

This ensures that all data points are correctly classified with a margin of at least 1. Figure 5 illustration of a linear SVM. The decision boundary separates two data classes and is placed midway between the nearest data points (support vectors). Dashed lines indicate the maximum margin.

Figure 5. Two-dimensional scatter plot with a linear separating hyperplane of the SVM

2.4.2. Soft margin SVM

In real-world scenarios, perfect separation may not be possible. Therefore, slack variables $\varepsilon_i \geq 0$ are introduced to allow some misclassification. The modified optimization problem becomes [39]:

$$\min_{w,b} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i \quad (14)$$

subject to:

$$y_i(w^T x_i + b) \geq 1 - \varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_i \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

where $C > 0$ is a regularization parameter that controls the trade-off between maximizing the margin and minimizing classification errors. Figure 6 two-dimensional plot illustrating the soft margin SVM, where some data points are allowed within or beyond the margin boundaries.

Figure 6. Two-dimensional plot of the support vector machine with a soft margin (soft margin SVM)

2.4.3. Non-linear SVM and kernel trick

When the data is not linearly separable in the original space, a non-linear mapping $\phi(x)$ is applied to project the data into a higher-dimensional feature space where linear separation may be possible. This is efficiently implemented using a kernel function $K(x_i, x_j)$ defined as [40]:

$$K(x_i, x_j) = \phi(x_i)^T \phi(x_j) \quad (16)$$

Common kernel functions include:

- Linear kernel: $K(x_i, x_j) = x_i^T x_j$
- Polynomial kernel: $K(x_i, x_j) = (x_i^T x_j + c)^d$
- Radial basis function (RBF) kernel: $K(x_i, x_j) = \exp(-\gamma \|x_i - x_j\|^2)$

In this study, the RBF kernel was used due to its ability to handle non-linear feature distributions typical in agricultural image data. Figure 7 visualization of a non-linear SVM using the kernel trick to project data into a higher-dimensional space for linear separation.

Figure 7. Visualization of a non-linear SVM and the application of the Kernel trick

2.4.4. Decision function

The final decision function used for classification is defined as:

$$f(x) = \text{sign}(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b) \quad (17)$$

where α_i are Lagrange multipliers determined during the training phase, and $K(x_i, x)$ computes the similarity between the support vectors and the test input.

The extracted features from the agricultural images—capturing texture, geometric structure, and keypoint-based descriptors—were used to train an SVM model with an RBF kernel. The model parameters C and γ were optimized using k-fold cross-validation to prevent overfitting and ensure generalization. The SVM classifier demonstrated high accuracy and robustness in distinguishing between different image categories based on the informative features. Figure 8 visualization of the SVM decision function and the margin boundaries defined by $f(x) = \pm 1$.

Figure 8. SVM decision function and margin boundaries

2.5. Evaluation metrics

To quantitatively assess the performance of the proposed image classification approach, several standard evaluation metrics were employed. These metrics provide insight into both the overall accuracy and the reliability of the classifier across different categories.

a. Accuracy

Accuracy is the proportion of correctly classified instances among the total number of samples. It is defined as:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (18)$$

where *TP* (*True Positives*): Number of correctly classified positive samples, *TN* (*True Negatives*): Number of correctly classified negative samples, *FP* (*False Positives*): Number of negative samples incorrectly classified as positive, *FN* (*False Negatives*): Number of positive samples incorrectly classified as negative. In this study, the SVM classifier achieved high accuracy in the test dataset, demonstrating high performance in distinguishing image classes based on the extracted informative features.

b. Precision, Recall, and F1-Score

In addition to accuracy, the following metrics were calculated:

– Precision:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (19)$$

Measures the proportion of positive identifications that were actually correct.

– Recall (Sensitivity)

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (20)$$

Measures the proportion of actual positives that were correctly identified.

– F1-Score

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (21)$$

Provides a harmonic mean of precision and recall, especially useful in imbalanced datasets.

c. Cross-validation

To ensure generalizability and avoid overfitting, k-fold cross-validation was performed with $k = 5$. The model maintained stable performance across all folds, indicating its robustness on unseen data.

3. RESULTS

Using the above methods, the results of the study will be as follows. It can be used in several fields, such as remote sensing of the Earth, early detection of diseases by tomato leaves - this, in turn, is a fast and effective result achieved using machine learning. To derive meaningful fractal characteristics from leaf images, a detailed preprocessing and feature extraction pipeline is essential. This multi-step approach processes raw leaf images into precise geometric metrics, which can be utilized for species identification and classification.

Figure 9 outlines the entire workflow for extracting informative features and conducting fractal analysis on a leaf sample. The process starts with Figure 9(a), where a contrast-enhanced binary image isolates the leaf structure from the background, providing a distinct silhouette for further examination. In Figure 9(b), the turn contours representation is displayed, highlighting the traced leaf boundary with key directional changes marked by blue, yellow, and red points connected by lines to emphasize significant geometric properties along the edge. Figure 9(c) demonstrates the calculation of the mean contour area through a vector-based overlay that accounts for the average spatial distribution of boundary features. Similarly, Figure 9(d) quantifies the standard deviation of the contour area, capturing variability in boundary complexity across different parts of the leaf and using a comparable vector notation. The process continues with Figure 9(e), which features the mean contour perimeter measurement, where vectors map characteristic distances along the leaf's edge. In Figure 9(f), the standard deviation of the contour perimeter highlights variations in boundary length across different regions, with denser vector clusters pinpointing areas of high geometric complexity, such as serrated edges. Figure 9(g) showcases the mean area-to-perimeter ratio—a

dimensionless metric indicating compactness and irregularity of boundary segments—through spatially distributed measurement vectors. Lastly, Figure 9(h) demonstrates fractal dimension analysis using the box-counting method. Seven iterations with progressively finer grid resolutions (box sizes from 2 to 128 pixels) are presented, illustrating a shift from coarse red grids to fine grayscale grids. Each iteration captures increasingly detailed boundary features, with count values displayed above each grid (ranging from 7 to 311). These values represent a power-law scaling relationship, enabling the computation of the fractal dimension.

Figure 9. Informative signs, (a) *contrast*, (b) *num_contours*, (c) *mean_contour_area*, (d) *std_contour_area*, (e) *mean_contour_perimeter*, (f) *std_contour_perimeter*, (g) *mean_area_to_perimeter_ratio*, (g) *mean_area_to_perimeter_ratio*, and (h) *fractal_dimension* (box-counting)

This detailed feature extraction method delivers a variety of complementary geometric descriptors that, when integrated, form a reliable signature for identifying leaves. Notably, the fractal dimension measurement provides a scale-invariant representation of boundary complexity, maintaining consistency regardless of changes in viewing distances or image resolutions.

Figure 10 outlines the visualization pipeline used to emphasize key informative features of a leaf specimen. In the left panel, the original image captures a green leaf set against a neutral gray backdrop, showcasing its venation patterns and serrated edges with clarity. Moving to the middle panel, the application of Canny edge detection transforms the leaf into a binary edge map. This step effectively highlights the complete boundary outline and internal vein structures as white lines on a black background, isolating the geometric framework of the leaf. Lastly, the right panel displays the results of ORB keypoints detection, where prominent features are marked on the original image using bright green circles and markers. These keypoints are predominantly located around the serrated edges of the leaf and at intersection points within the venation network, identifying areas of notable geometric intricacy and structural uniqueness. Their spatial arrangement emphasizes that the most significant features arise at points of pronounced curvature changes and texture variation, rather than in the more uniform central regions of the leaf.

Figure 10. Visualization that highlights informative features

These capabilities allow images to be assessed in terms of their texture, structure, geometric characteristics, and fractal complexity. The resulting data can be used to analyze, classify, or identify patterns in images. Let's consider the results of image research, which are used in several fields when highlighting informative features of an object in an image. A quick and effective result can be obtained with early detection of the disease through tomato leaves. Let's add the above image to the vector representation in the table to facilitate calculations. It can be seen that Table 1 highlights the feature without normalization, and Table 2 highlights it after normalization.

Remote sensing is a method of obtaining information about the Earth's surface and its changes using instruments mounted on satellites, airplanes, or unmanned aerial vehicles. This process involves taking

images and measuring various characteristics of the Earth's surface-such as terrain, vegetation, temperature, humidity, and other parameters-without direct physical contact with the object being observed. Remote sensing data is widely used in fields such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, cartography, geology, natural resource management, and emergency response.

The feature extraction methodology, while predominantly demonstrated using botanical specimens, exhibits a versatile application across various domains, including geospatial and remote sensing analysis. The computational techniques, particularly edge detection and keypoint extraction algorithms, prove efficacious for examining intricate natural patterns at diverse spatial scales, spanning from microscopic leaf structures to extensive terrain configurations.

Table 1. Table in the form of vectors before normalization

Classes	contrast	num_contours	mean_contour_area	std_contour_area	mean_contour_perimeter	std_contour_perimeter	mean_area_to_perimeter_ratio	fractal_dimension
Healthy	37.36588247504914	745	41.673154362	1096.158809	8.330579827	83.116454927	0.069898376262	1.9015853296
Healthy	49.92771511928245	75	799.96	6858.562852	45.57271534	309.37147289	0.387901362635	1.9007252278
Healthy	44.800203163762916	1070	31.042523364	921.8226545	11.55998361	133.91557719	0.052316928614	1.9556830542
Healthy	35.32940780603492	1242	26.270128824	897.8260553	6.992370426	103.71063206	0.032662478234	1.9420276684
Healthy	36.33191702294344	1291	25.538729666	884.1931264	6.707476758	91.272370811	0.031870865753	1.9437245964
Healthy	51.038177014839626	830	37.859638554	1050.186030	10.27192246	145.63491861	0.047664516223	1.9190272444
Healthy	51.80684926493237	507	61.188362919	1344.055329	11.74123455	125.64160858	0.058907243655	1.8830814944
Healthy	38.43759350132606	1107	28.365853658	907.8612297	6.858337591	73.441080533	0.040485004800	1.9260870754
Healthy	39.368361543602774	1240	25.129838709	848.3892383	6.508126003	76.177331564	0.038053655871	1.9306454133
Healthy	38.427830200702935	1107	28.365853658	907.8612297	6.858337591	73.441080533	0.040485004800	1.9260870754
First stage	39.273999725351175	1151	27.804083405	901.1011957	6.915189238	71.410153756	0.039857619859	1.9322419918
First stage	52.574191866971965	746	40.354557640	1048.168157	12.17192235	159.29330957	0.055207835424	1.9124510072
First stage	57.72404060686768	134	199.17910447	2290.542996	26.64659788	252.77808826	0.096436608361	1.8154330077
First stage	44.60543626083	1061	30.922714420	913.9804572	11.99331322	151.25996205	0.052012221871	1.9560939503
First stage	36.850640038076165	925	35.019459459	875.3959500	13.16857907	73.773105269	0.097102098866	1.9482650268
First stage	38.08730485055974	919	34.727965179	860.3282270	14.26350399	88.300246560	0.089033445673	1.9497392751
First stage	36.850228013990964	925	35.019459459	875.3959500	13.16857907	73.773105269	0.097102098866	1.9482650268
First stage	37.981698385328215	881	36.147559591	887.8118660	14.58813381	93.496715143	0.093238970979	1.9499467056
First stage	48.92713047500953	124	206.52822580	2274.736007	16.74269818	127.89865018	0.199076223730	1.7870345881
First stage	37.34119746046685	1443	24.197158697	867.3857943	8.667020413	101.71834110	0.042667114635	1.9709397658
Second stage	39.10591685280323	1377	25.344952795	887.9329218	9.792837373	127.36523494	0.041119528492	1.9731529065
Second stage	38.883401942783486	1438	23.944367176	855.7981179	9.049501862	100.33991615	0.043926147823	1.9714532246
Second stage	57.7517752608782	678	51.416666666	1247.227874	15.82244071	180.83996105	0.059434476041	1.9388854743
Second stage	38.72333697675324	214	165.38317757	2375.864990	26.32458263	247.41023763	0.101063525668	1.8891355810
Second stage	61.990945474076625	405	94.475308641	1872.799461	18.66859204	261.19016418	0.058761544720	1.9252923799
Second stage	48.82860902130554	480	76.351041666	1633.104460	16.81595203	208.06915011	0.072378797423	1.9268975575
Second stage	49.659731961609914	464	78.337284482	1630.156895	18.12171400	196.44569501	0.079360119212	1.9275725718
Second stage	64.78210838493861	200	178.595	2496.776985	21.18620608	245.21243202	0.098907925595	1.89111743632
Second stage	65.30879297094319	132	246.93560606	2803.693101	25.01716114	211.53595109	0.173533073466	1.8533187558
Second stage	38.33655877460931	1092	32.548534798	1038.256717	8.528816192	116.44484812	0.046228123066	1.9526010944

Table 2. Table in the form of vectors after normalization

Classes	contrast	num_cont_ours	mean_contour_area	std_contour_area	mean_contour_perimeter	std_contour_perimeter	mean_area_to_perimeter_ratio	fractal_dimension
Healthy	0.52	0.002	0.019	0.022	0.214	0.002	0.794	0.52
Healthy	0.319	0.005	0.042	0.046	0.326	0.004	0.754	0.319
Healthy	0.267	0.006	0.049	0.032	0.161	0.015	0.701	0.267
Healthy	0.246	0.007	0.052	0.036	0.164	0.016	0.703	0.246
Healthy	0.576	0.002	0.019	0.022	0.218	0.001	0.861	0.576
Healthy	0.349	0.005	0.037	0.038	0.203	0.006	0.777	0.349
Healthy	0.075	0.046	0.231	0.091	0.441	0.021	0.91	0.075
Healthy	0.75	0.001	0.012	0.018	0.126	0.002	0.943	0.75
Healthy	0.118	0.016	0.084	0.104	0.537	0.009	0.5	0.118
Healthy	0.809	0.001	0.009	0.019	0.157	0.002	0.977	0.809
First stage	0.322	0.005	0.046	0.036	0.3	0.006	0.781	0.322
First stage	0.516	0.002	0.012	0.02	0.043	0.006	0.687	0.516
First stage	0.317	0.005	0.041	0.051	0.358	0.005	0.762	0.317
First stage	0.484	0.002	0.013	0.027	0.108	0.005	0.698	0.484
First stage	0.228	0.007	0.042	0.053	0.277	0.009	0.56	0.228
First stage	0.532	0.002	0.023	0.016	0.157	0.003	0.782	0.532
First stage	0.553	0.002	0.016	0.016	0.211	0.001	0.72	0.553
First stage	0.929	0.0	0.0	0.018	0.115	0.002	0.941	0.929
First stage	0.062	0.028	0.116	0.091	0.353	0.023	0.257	0.062
First stage	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.008	0.047	0.0	0.891	1.0
Second stage	0.981	0.0	0.001	0.009	0.058	0.001	0.902	0.981
Second stage	0.71	0.001	0.013	0.029	0.146	0.003	1.0	0.71
Second stage	0.762	0.001	0.008	0.027	0.167	0.002	0.984	0.762
Second stage	0.319	0.005	0.042	0.046	0.326	0.004	0.754	0.319
Second stage	0.406	0.004	0.037	0.047	0.343	0.005	0.92	0.406
Second stage	0.252	0.006	0.034	0.065	0.326	0.011	0.655	0.252
Second stage	0.105	0.031	0.18	0.122	0.552	0.015	0.936	0.105
Second stage	0.075	0.045	0.227	0.124	0.557	0.02	0.951	0.075
Second stage	0.283	0.005	0.016	0.053	0.211	0.009	0.669	0.283
Second stage	0.828	0.001	0.006	0.01	0.017	0.002	0.84	0.828

Figure 11 exemplifies the utilization of the feature extraction pipeline on an earth remote sensing image obtained via satellite. In the leftmost panel, the original image showcases a meandering river system characterized by sinuous curves traversing heterogeneous terrain such as forested areas (denoted by green-brown regions) and water bodies (depicted in blue). This imagery, sourced via Google Earth, serves as a practical case study to assess the robustness of geometric feature extraction algorithms in identifying natural fractal patterns. The middle panel illustrates the application of the Canny edge detection technique, effectively delineating the complex boundaries of the river and surrounding terrain features with white edge outlines against a black background. This outcome highlights the algorithm's capability in tracing the river's intricate meanders and branching patterns, embodying the self-similar characteristics typical of natural waterways.

In the rightmost panel, ORB keypoints detection is represented through bright green markers superimposed on the original satellite image. These markers are predominantly concentrated along the river's course and at branching intersections, pinpointing areas of elevated geometric complexity where structural curvature and directional variations are most prominent. Such findings underscore the efficacy of feature extraction methodologies in providing nuanced insights into the spatial organization of natural systems.

Figure 11. Earth remote sensing image

In Table 3, the selection of features is carried out without normalization, whereas Table 4 shows the results after normalization of the data. The results obtained during the study represent an important stage, given the importance of the informative features of the image. They contribute to achieving high classification accuracy while reducing the time spent on its implementation.

Table 3. Table in the form of vectors before normalization

Classes	contrast	num_co ntours	mean_contour area	std_contour_ area	mean_conto ur_perimeter	std_contour_ perimeter	mean_area_to_ perimeter_ratio	fractal dime nsion
River	41.579241 258787164	356	92.676966292 13484	1725.514929 536606	13.39729790 774624	178.9384372 1429133	0.06561092475 978911	1.88423111 0988124
River	56.344880 469028105	424	76.067216981 13208	1391.398560 7287061	10.50240280 3526735	109.8762436 9138233	0.06799473008 265143	1.88283169 1810061
River	34.451080 17051144	807	44.351920693 92813	1231.001382 376676	6.159621827 368991	88.92491196 611734	0.04467432071 4744475	1.92204599 38532337
River	23.756907 041875834	106	365.11792452 83019	3690.835168 149927	28.61598781 369767	217.1344290 5071608	0.30046454816 201057	1.87626306 51870513
River	48.836862 005475844	1129	27.232506643 046943	856.3461536 745542	6.107549364 319726	71.96252663 718285	0.03404462077 599574	1.92102219 67360916
River	29.892062 869046782	191	167.53403141 361255	2271.712281 2170646	17.43102739 8059506	165.1211445 7696077	0.14271972660 807225	1.86435394 48644586
River	63.549698 62628099	814	36.417076167 07617	948.3267863 328883	8.709786703 7506	72.60089266 187208	0.06080565082 6632286	1.90654759 45763684
River	44.897363 58550866	930	36.429569892 47312	1068.867869 6301859	9.070762598 770921	122.8510200 688499	0.04773615862 623374	1.93100376 7361902
River	49.143693 35632184	964	30.929979253 112034	868.0745702 807158	9.514807352 139247	94.42718911 101834	0.05300327151 522794	1.92375683 89445021
River	27.901166 235867635	275	119.41636363 636364	1915.860158 6625298	12.28654299 4325812	89.94536370 12741	0.16882338988 968654	1.87200694 81494108
Hirhway	24.297871 127189143	382	97.098167539 26701	1881.065521 1725839	12.62681988 1469167	171.7896730 3188227	0.08045482259 770706	1.90285743 53750936
Hirhway	30.175713 281400608	514	62.595330739 29961	1400.208319 220948	10.48518162 2700004	157.0159388 289095	0.05910165107 639241	1.89472556 65501204
Hirhway	20.757009 600171084	113	301.48230088 495575	3140.885321 2838976	26.21504213 0082054	182.8915980 2793318	0.32160021440 524045	1.86375935 05343975
Hirhway	54.922013 71141501	604	52.011589403 97351	1223.344301 3587835	9.621697483 473266	142.0082352 7656254	0.04014155482 530131	1.89897184 56210611
Hirhway	59.447483 75742923	553	55.531645569 62025	1080.829686 994994	12.60104258 0647666	102.9990607 9962143	0.07953180842 282428	1.89902126 78125535
Hirhway	43.010927 24014021	458	70.151746724 89083	1362.974156 671575	17.10592951 5507544	183.2987638 2125718	0.09104375200 685441	1.90759656 24867124
Hirhway	63.939397 578341016	384	85.2109375 4061832	1312.688667 4061832	17.43903036 9122822	135.7155945 2354566	0.10704124585 914597	1.89901328 33897535
Hirhway	45.740507 14140135	76	277.89473684 210526	2377.237781 372075	28.24101323 0461824	186.3268409 792821	0.24690430716 452835	1.75633957 81215114
Hirhway	57.477367 984442445	651	48.653609831 029186	1058.520620 5867694	9.034160144 134967	91.66209372 75507	0.06539159168 850626	1.90109159 64546966
Hirhway	25.990904 866471766	423	76.812056737 58865	1526.210201 3626838	11.29450880 7484421	128.5072022 4618917	0.06775797271 339992	1.88046408 2498345
AnnualCrop	23.521178 89312911	839	38.318831942 78903	1084.776478 4961537	6.205419281 952714	82.99917113 90823	0.05463990302 945312	1.90453545 63684471
AnnualCrop	42.235088 76458446	1	10827.5	0.0	866.5067014 694214	0.0	12.4955756044 80305	1.60836616 7279685
AnnualCrop	43.405379 01230686	282	117.49290780 141844	1921.273724 2136936	15.72740921 6106361	152.9717181 5593236	0.10934435175 738975	1.87612119 6082828
AnnualCrop	41.187467 7539537	499	63.951903807 61523	1365.094325 2115703	12.49303617 744981	140.6187668 7049383	0.08226881618 9977	1.89872287 9604376
AnnualCrop	28.531614 93114735	554	57.234657039 711195	1302.641542 5040664	9.952087561 576375	122.3557550 9524085	0.06123971034 688353	1.89153337 0851744
AnnualCrop	29.794017 77726525	297	120.04882154 882155	2031.679662 0776508	14.58836573 3824194	136.3387540 2526002	0.11259615364 77045	1.87596251 82737625
AnnualCrop	25.004273 458250772	210	154.88809523 809525	2214.233396 439024	16.01344622 032983	164.5120770 230593	0.13595647763 877985	1.86602967 01012185
AnnualCrop	44.203035 70389019	908	35.161894273 12775	995.8026433 018665	7.523445194 513262	71.12345634 409719	0.04682321850 412369	1.91632892 2102328
AnnualCrop	21.493743 46913745	264	130.62310606 060606	2081.509554 066629	12.15476589 9434235	129.9488010 4072072	0.12477175164 04765	1.87879104 11441144
AnnualCrop	51.116627 796838806	904	34.133296460 17699	844.2598369 11002	9.375726742 02708	80.34545780 024825	0.05932462245 757251	1.92002631 47467795

Table 4. The table in the form of vectors after normalization

Classes	contrast	num_cont ours	mean_conto ur area	std_contour_ area	mean_contour perimeter	std_contour_ perimeter	mean_area_to_ perimeter ratio	fractal_dime nsion
River	0.448	0.297	0.001	0.053	0.008	0.32	0.001	0.739
River	0.755	0.354	0.001	0.043	0.005	0.197	0.001	0.736
River	0.3	0.675	0.0	0.038	0.001	0.159	0.0	0.825
River	0.078	0.088	0.005	0.114	0.023	0.389	0.004	0.722
River	0.599	0.945	0.0	0.026	0.001	0.129	0.0	0.822
River	0.205	0.159	0.002	0.07	0.012	0.296	0.002	0.695
River	0.905	0.681	0.0	0.029	0.003	0.13	0.001	0.79
River	0.517	0.778	0.0	0.033	0.004	0.22	0.0	0.845
River	0.605	0.807	0.0	0.027	0.004	0.169	0.0	0.829
River	0.164	0.229	0.001	0.059	0.007	0.161	0.002	0.712
Hirhway	0.089	0.319	0.001	0.058	0.007	0.308	0.001	0.781
Hirhway	0.211	0.43	0.001	0.043	0.005	0.281	0.0	0.763
Hirhway	0.015	0.094	0.004	0.097	0.021	0.328	0.005	0.693
Hirhway	0.725	0.505	0.0	0.038	0.004	0.254	0.0	0.773
Hirhway	0.82	0.462	0.0	0.033	0.007	0.184	0.001	0.773
Hirhway	0.478	0.383	0.001	0.042	0.012	0.328	0.001	0.792
Hirhway	0.913	0.321	0.001	0.04	0.012	0.243	0.001	0.768
Hirhway	0.535	0.063	0.004	0.073	0.023	0.334	0.003	0.451
Hirhway	0.779	0.544	0.0	0.033	0.004	0.164	0.001	0.777
Hirhway	0.124	0.353	0.001	0.047	0.006	0.23	0.001	0.731
AnnualCrop	0.073	0.702	0.0	0.033	0.001	0.149	0.0	0.785
AnnualCrop	0.462	0.0	0.166	0.0	0.849	0.0	0.196	0.118
AnnualCrop	0.486	0.235	0.001	0.059	0.01	0.274	0.001	0.721
AnnualCrop	0.44	0.417	0.001	0.042	0.007	0.252	0.001	0.772
AnnualCrop	0.177	0.463	0.0	0.04	0.005	0.219	0.001	0.756
AnnualCrop	0.203	0.248	0.001	0.063	0.009	0.244	0.001	0.721
AnnualCrop	0.103	0.175	0.002	0.068	0.011	0.295	0.002	0.698
AnnualCrop	0.503	0.76	0.0	0.031	0.002	0.127	0.0	0.812
AnnualCrop	0.03	0.22	0.002	0.064	0.007	0.233	0.002	0.727
AnnualCrop	0.646	0.756	0.0	0.026	0.004	0.144	0.0	0.82

Using the informative features of this training sample, we train the SVM algorithm:

- a. Illustration of a linear SVM: two groups of points (class -1 in blue and class +1 in red) are separated by a decision boundary. The dashed lines represent the margin boundaries $f(x) = \pm 1$. The circled points are the support vectors that define the position of the hyperplane and the width of the margin. Figure 12
- Illustration of a linear SVM: two-point classes (-1: blue, +1: red) are separated by a linear decision boundary. Dashed lines represent the margins $f(x) = \pm 1$, and circled support vectors determine the hyperplane and its margin width.
- b. Illustration of SVM with an RBF kernel: two groups of points (class -1 in blue and class +1 in red) are separated by a non-linear decision boundary. The shaded regions indicate the classification areas, and the black-outlined circles represent the support vectors that define the shape of the boundary. The RBF kernel function provides an implicit mapping of features into a higher-dimensional space where the classes become separable.

Figure 12. SVM (Linear kernel) with margin equations

Figure 13 shows the SVM with an RBF kernel. Two classes of points (−1: blue, +1: red) are separated by a non-linear decision boundary. Shaded regions represent classification zones, while black-circled points indicate the support vectors that define the shape of the boundary. The RBF kernel enables implicit feature mapping into a higher-dimensional space where the classes become linearly separable.

Figure 13. Non-linear SVM classification with RBF kernel

To assess the performance of the classification model, a confusion matrix is utilized to provide a comprehensive analysis of prediction accuracy across all classes. This tool not only highlights the overall accuracy but also uncovers specific misclassification patterns that can guide improvements to the model. Figure 14 illustrates the confusion matrix for the results of the multi-class classification task. The matrix is structured with actual class labels (0 to 4) along the vertical axis and predicted class labels on the horizontal axis. Each cell indicates the sample count, where diagonal cells represent correct classifications, and off-diagonal cells signify errors. The color gradient, ranging from white (indicating zero counts) to dark blue (representing higher counts), offers an intuitive visual representation of classification performance.

Figure 14. Confusion matrix

Class 0 demonstrates outstanding accuracy, with 162 correctly classified samples and only one misclassified as class 2. Class 1 performs well, achieving 89 correct predictions, though 3 instances were incorrectly assigned to class 2. Class 2 shows solid results with 101 correct classifications, but some challenges are evident—8 samples were misclassified as class 1, 1 as class 3, and 2 as class 4. For class 3, 69 instances were accurately classified; however, there is significant misclassification with 14 samples

confused with class 4, alongside a smaller number of errors spread across classes 0, 1, and 2. Finally, class 4 shows the strongest performance, recording 193 correct predictions with minimal errors—4 samples misclassified as class 2 and 8 as class 3.

The experimental evaluation demonstrated that the proposed approach achieved a classification accuracy of 93% with a loss value of 0.07. These results confirm the effectiveness of the applied feature extraction methods combined with the SVM classifier, ensuring both high precision and stability. Such performance highlights the practical applicability of the method for solving real-world image analysis tasks, particularly in the agricultural domain.

Beyond the visualization of the confusion matrix, a detailed classification report offers essential performance metrics for each class, enabling a quantitative evaluation of the model's strengths and weaknesses across various criteria. The classification report associated with Figure 15 provides precision, recall, F1-score, and support values for all five classes (0 through 4).

For Class 0, the performance is outstanding, with precision, recall, and F1-score all at 0.99 across 163 samples. This indicates near-perfect classification with negligible false positives or false negatives. Class 1 exhibits solid results as well, achieving a precision of 0.88 and a recall of 0.97, culminating in an F1-score of 0.92 over 92 samples. While overall strong, this class displays slightly more false positive predictions.

Class 2 delivers balanced performance, reporting a precision of 0.93, a recall of 0.89, and an F1-score of 0.91 for its 113 samples, reflecting relatively equal rates of false positives and false negatives. Conversely, Class 3 fares the weakest, with its precision at 0.88, recall at 0.78, and F1-score at 0.83 across 88 samples. These figures indicate that Class 3 is the most challenging for the model to classify correctly, facing higher confusion with other classes. In contrast, Class 4 demonstrates strong performance consistency, with precision at 0.92, recall at 0.94, and an F1-score of 0.93 across 205 samples, the largest subset, highlighting reliable performance.

When evaluating the overall model performance, an accuracy of 0.93 is achieved over all 661 samples. The macro average—representing unweighted mean scores across all classes—reports precision, recall, and F1-score values of 0.92 each. Meanwhile, the weighted average—which accounts for class imbalances—shows slightly higher values of 0.93 for precision, recall, and F1-score. The improved results in the weighted average suggest that the model performs particularly well on classes with larger sample sizes.

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.99	0.99	0.99	163
1	0.88	0.97	0.92	92
2	0.93	0.89	0.91	113
3	0.88	0.78	0.83	88
4	0.92	0.94	0.93	205
accuracy			0.93	661
macro avg	0.92	0.92	0.92	661
weighted avg	0.93	0.93	0.93	661

Figure 15. Classification report

The relationship between model accuracy and loss offers valuable insights into the trade-off between classification performance and prediction confidence. Visualizing these two complementary metrics together allows a better evaluation of whether the model has achieved an optimal balance between accurate predictions and minimal error.

Figure 16 presents model accuracy and loss as interconnected metrics. The horizontal axis is divided into two evaluation criteria: "Accuracy" on the left and "Loss" on the right, while the vertical axis represents metric values, ranging from 0.0 to 1.0. The blue line links the two points, starting at an accuracy value of approximately 0.93 (93%) and declining to a loss value of around 0.07. This inverse relationship is both expected and indicative of a well-trained classification model—high accuracy paired with low loss reflects correct predictions made with strong confidence. The exact values beneath the graph (Accuracy: 0.93, Loss: 0.07) quantify the model's performance, indicating it successfully classifies 93% of test samples while maintaining an error rate of just 7%. The sharp downward slope of the connecting line underscores the pronounced inverse correlation, highlighting that the model has likely reached a stable and effective state.

Figure 16. Model accuracy and loss

The observed accuracy-loss relationship demonstrates that the model has been trained efficiently, exhibiting no evidence of overfitting or underfitting. The concurrent presence of high accuracy and low loss values highlights the model's strong generalization ability, reflecting its capacity to produce confident and accurate predictions on the test dataset. These performance indicators are further supported by the detailed analysis provided in the confusion matrix and classification report, which collectively validate the robustness and dependability of the classification system.

4. DISCUSSION

It should be noted separately that the above results were previously used by many researchers in their works and were accompanied by obtaining various results. In particular, a number of scientific publications devoted to the application of machine learning methods in medicine, early detection of diseases from images of leaves, as well as their widespread use in other areas, emphasized that one of the serious problems remains the lack of interpretability of models. This study focuses on short-term feature processing, which plays a key role in achieving high performance. An analysis conducted in another study came to the following conclusions: i) Classification by informative features allows to significantly reduce processing time; and ii) Results are achieved quickly and with high efficiency. However, the reliability that these studies rely on has not been confirmed in our study. Moreover, not only the reliability, but also the universality of the application of the corresponding methods to all machine learning algorithms, not just artificial neural networks, remains questionable.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the technology of extraction of informative features from images based on the technologies ORB and fractal analysis. Those technologies carry certain advantages and may be effectively used for a wide range of problems. ORB technology guarantees fast and effective detection and description of interest points, which is particularly valuable when there is a necessity to use those applications where there is a requirement for a fast speed of information processing and resistance to rotation of objects. Fractal analysis allows the detection of features due to the geometric nature and the degree of complexity of the structure of the image, which is particularly valuable when there is a necessity to analyze objects having an uneven and complex texture.

Both methods were found to be effective and practical for computer vision and image processing challenges, providing stable and precise outcomes under varied conditions. Experiments on the feature extraction methods such as ORB and fractal analysis confirmed their practicality and real-world applicability. The ORB method was found to be a viable tool for precise and efficient extraction of scale-rotation invariant features. Fractal analysis helped us obtain broad understanding on the nature of images through the analysis of textural characteristics and fractal dimensions. The use of ORB and fractal analysis approaches to informative features extraction demonstrated their strong effectiveness when used in image processing

problems. ORB demonstrated an efficient and rapid approach to the detection of keypoints and building the construction of descriptors, which is particularly valuable when dealing with extensive datasets in real time. Fractal analysis opened an invaluable possibility to research the complex and irregular images' structures, opening the deeper insight into their geometric complexity. Thus, the use of both methods opens the gateway towards the continued development of computer vision and computer-driven image processing technologies.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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- Mirzaakbar Hidayberdiev: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft.
- Baxodir Achilov: Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualization, Project administration.
- Nurmukhammad Alimkulov: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing – Original Draft.
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Mirzaakbar Hidayberdiev	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓	✓					
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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nterpretation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. This research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest. No funding organizations had any role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study. All participants were fully informed about the purpose of the research, the procedures involved, and their right to withdraw at any time. Written consent forms were collected and stored securely in accordance with ethical guidelines and data protection regulations.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was not required for this study. The research involved only the analysis of leaf specimens and satellite imagery, with no human participants or animal subjects involved in the experimental procedures.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are not publicly available due to privacy and confidentiality restrictions. Data are available from the authors upon reasonable request and with permission of the appropriate institutional authority.

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